

Greener Journal of Plant Breeding and Crop Science

ISSN: 2354-2292

Submission Date: 06/01/014

Acceptance: 28/07/014

Publication: 29/07/014

Liming Effects on Yield and Yield Components of Haricot Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Varieties Grown in Acidic Soil at Damot Sore District, Southern Ethiopia

By

**Mesfin Kassa
Belay Yebo
Abera Habte**

Research Article

Liming Effects on Yield and Yield Components of Haricot Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Varieties Grown in Acidic Soil at Damot Sore District, Southern Ethiopia

***Mesfin Kassa, Belay Yebo and Abera Habte**

Wolaita Sodo University, College of Agriculture, P.O.BOX 138, Wolaita Sodo, Ethiopia.

*Corresponding Author's Email: mesfine2004@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted at location Damot Sore in Wolaita Zone, Southern Nations Nationalities and People's Regional State (SNNPRS) to evaluate the response of varieties haricot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) with two rates of lime (0 and 0.4 t ha⁻¹ CaCO₃) used on acidic soils. The treatments were arranged in factorial RCBD with three replications. Analysis resulted of soil samples showed that Organic carbon, Availability phosphorus, Total nitrogen and Soil pH values were very low. Application of lime resulted in significant changes on these chemical properties of the soils in the location. Availability of P and soil pH was improved due to the application of lime and maximum values of these parameters were recorded. Growth parameters, yield and yield components were significantly increased with increasing rates of liming at the location (year1&2). Maximum grain yields 1282.49 kg ha⁻¹ for Hawasa Dume at Gununo and 1079.40 kg ha⁻¹ for Omo-95 were recorded with rates of 20 kg Pha⁻¹ with lime (0.4 t ha⁻¹) at location. From the result of this study it could be conclude that liming improve soil pH, Availability phosphorus and performance of haricot bean varieties but till now there is some gap on correcting acidity of the soils and also grain yield of the varieties. So application of lime should be repeated in the coming season until soil comes to neutral and increased the production of the crops.

Keywords: Hawasa Dume, Omo-95, soil acidity, yield.

1. INTRODUCTION

Haricot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is annual pulse crop with considerable variation in habit, vegetation characters, flower color and the size, shape of pods and seeds (Onwueme and Sinha, 1999). It was probably first cultivated with maize, and it seems likely that the two crops evolved together in a cereal-Legume farming system in much the same way as cowpeas and sorghum in West Africa. It is widely cultivated throughout different parts of Ethiopia. It is produced in four major agro ecological zones, including the central, eastern, southern and western zones. Haricot bean is mainly used as source of food and cash. It is exported to earn foreign exchange and is also one of the cash crops locally used by farmers as source of food. Additionally farmers also grow the bean to use as forage for livestock and mulching. Haricot bean cultivation can be carried out without large input and intensive practices and this makes it suitable for poor farmers where the need in food supply is important. It can be used in intercropping system with maize and between young trees until canopy closure.

Yield of legumes in farmer's field is usually less than 0.65t/ha against the potential yield of 1.2t/ha suggesting a large yield gap (CACC, 2002). Low yield potential of legumes has made them less competitive with cereals and other high value crops. The yield of haricot bean increase with P application and its nodulation and fixation of N can be also improved with the application of P (Gemechu, 1990). The average national productivity of haricot bean is 0.72t/ha (CACC, 2002) and its regional productivity is 0.81t/ha.

The major haricot bean producing area in the southern zone includes Gamo Goffa, Sidamo and Wolaita (Gemechu, 1990). Haricot bean is also one of the most communal cultivated pulse crops in the Wolaita area where its yield is lower than regional and national yields. The low yield is contributed from acidity of soils which reduce availability of P and basic cations as Ca and Mg and also affect activities of soil microorganisms (Havlin *et al.*, 1999).

Lime application neutralizes soil acidity, reduces toxicity levels of Al, Fe and Mn and improves physiological, chemical and biological properties of soils (Kisinyo *et al.*, 2005). It also improves soil productivity by providing Ca and Mg (Oster, 1982). It is found that as the lime and P application to acid soils increased plant available Fe, Mn, Zn and

Cu, but B contents of soil decreased, whereas pH, Ca, Mg and available P increased which in turn improve crop performance (Ponette *et al.*, 1996). The extension of this approach in semiarid region of Ethiopia appears to be promising. Even though application of lime is brings a positive effect on soil conditions and crop performance, in Wolaita area where the problem of soil acidity is very chronic, little or no work is done to verify whether there is response of crops to P application rates with liming or not. Furthermore, to use lime as source of nutrients, there should be site specific recommendation to maintain optimum level of nutrients. Therefore, this study was initiated with the following objectives.

- To evaluate the response of haricot bean varieties to different rates of liming
- To compare the performance of haricot bean varieties with liming

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Description of the Study Site

The research was conducted during the 2012-2013 rainy season at location, which is located in Wolaita Zone, Southern Nations Nationalities and People's Regional State. The location was Damot sore district, which is located 348 km south of Addis Ababa and 2 km from Gununo town, at 6°56'N and 37°39' E and altitude of 1790 meters above sea level. The peak rainy months are April, July, August and September. The mean minimum and maximum temperatures are 15°C and 26 °C, respectively. The representative date was collected from Areka Agricultural Research Center.

2.2. Methods and approaches

To fill the knowledge gap on application of liming with fertilizer rate on acidic soil, various knowledge enhancement activities were carried out. They included training of 30 subject matter specialists, 30 farmers and 8 development workers, introduction of liming application on acidic soils on selected two farmers training centers in two woredas.

2.3. Treatments and Experimental Design

Hawassa Dume and Omo-95 haricot bean varieties were used for test crop to compare its response to liming rate (0 & 0.4 tha^{-1} CaCO_3). The treatments were arranged in factorial RCBD with three replication. Five rows each have fifteen plants were used on plot having size of 2.0 m by 1.5 m. Spacing of 10, 40, 50 and 100 cm were used between plants, rows, plots and blocks, respectively. Urea at rate of 50 N kg ha^{-1} and 20 P kg ha^{-1} were applied at planting time. TSP for P and urea for N were used as source of fertilizer.

2.4. Agronomic Data Collection

Flowering and maturity dates (when 50% of the plants were at respective phenological stage), number of branches per plant, plant height, number of pods per plant, number of leaf per plants, pod length, number of seeds per pod and seed yield were recorded. Three central rows were harvested for determination of grain yield and total biomass.

2.5. Soil Sampling and Analysis

The soil samples were air-dried and ground to pass 2 and 0.5 mm (for total N) sieves. All samples were analyzed following standard laboratory procedures as outlined by (Sahlemedhin *et al.*, 2000). Organic carbon and total N contents of the soil were determined following the wet combustion method of Walkley and Black, and wet digestion procedure of Kjeldahl method, respectively. Available P was extracted by Olsen method. Soil texture was analyzed by Bouyoucos hydrometer method. The pH (H_2O) of the soils was measured in water using pH meter with glass-calomel combination electrode.

2.6. Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from soil and crops were statistically analyzed using the PROC ANOVA function of SAS and means were compared using LSD at a probability level of 5%.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physicochemical Properties of Soil

Soil analysis of the two locations before sowing in two years (Table 1) showed that pH values (5.0 and 5.6) found in the range of strong acid based on Herrera (2005) classification. Whereas the application of lime resulted in a significant increase in soil pH compared to 0 t/ha, the application of lime combined with P 20 kg/ha led to slight decrease soil acidity in both year1 & 2, but this was not significant (Table 1). This result clearly indicated that the area is seriously affected by soil acidity, which is not satisfactory for growth of most crops (Havlin *et al.*, 1999). Soil analysis results of soil sample showed that pH values at harvested were higher than values before sowing both in year1&2, which may be attributed to application of P fertilizer and the positive effect of lime in neutralizing acid soils.

The range of available phosphorous contents of the location (0.6 mg kg^{-1}) before sowing was very low (Table 1) this range was very low based on (Herrera, 2005). This low concentration of available P may be related to acidity of the soil which bring fixation of P (Havlin *et al.*, 1999). The available phosphorous concentration increased with increased liming. The highest concentration of Av.P (5.2 mg/kg) was recorded under year 2 in Gununo site whereas the lowest Av.P was found at year 1 at 0 t/ha liming at location. The differences in Av.P concentration in soil might be resulted from changes in biological and geochemical processes at different activities after human disturbances.

Application of lime might contributed in releasing some amount of fixed P to be available for the crop. But application of lime alone could not help haricot bean production to be increased. This also indicates that deficiency of P cannot be replaced by lime. As a result in acidic soils which are deficient in Av.P, OC and TN are important to apply P together with lime to increase crop production and there were no significant differences on TN and OC of soils in both locations. On the other hand, application of lime resulted significant variation on soil pH and available P in the two locations of year1 & 2. These changes of soil pH and Av.P of soil may be attributed to the neutralizing of acid soil due to application of lime and also application of P fertilizer at increasing rates (Tisdale *et al.*, 1993). First year and second years lime application with fertilizer had been affected by haricot bean production. This is in agreement with Anetor and Ezekiel (2007) who indicated that lime increased pH and available P in Nigeria. However, potassium and exchangeable acidity were decreased with increasing application. Textural analysis showed that the same textural class according to the present study soil textural class was sandy loam in both locations and there are no significantly differences between year 1 & 2. The lack of soil textural class difference between year 1 & 2 at both years its might be attributed to the similarity in parent material from which the soils originate.

Table 1. Physiochemical properties of the soil before sowing at Gununo, 2012-2014

location	Soil pH		Av. p (mg/kg)		TN %		OC		Textural class
	yr1	yr 2	yr1	yr 2	yr1	yr 2	yr1	yr 2	
Gununo	5.0	5.4	0.60	5.22	0.12	0.18	0.10	1.70	Sandy loam

The dates were year 1&2 contents of the soil exhibited an increasing trend with increasing rates of liming material application. The lime (0.4 t ha^{-1}) produced the highest mean phosphorus concentration, implying a greater effect of the applied lime material on the availability of phosphorus in two years. Therefore; applying higher amounts of liming materials in acidic soils maximized the availability of phosphorus nutrient in the soils, which is very important for crop production (Smith *et al.*, 1994).

3.2. Interaction effect of lime on growth performance of haricot bean varieties

Application of lime at different rates resulted in significant variation on growth parameter of plant in the two locations both with and without lime (Table 2). Growth parameters such as plant height, leaf and branches number were increased significantly with liming. Maximum values of plant heights, leaf and branches numbers were recorded at application rates of 20 kgPha^{-1} in the location both with and without liming; Hawassa Duma had better performance than Omo-95. In line with this result Kisinyo *et al.* (2005) indicated that growth of plant increased in acid soil as application of P increased with and without lime. This positive growth response of haricot bean for application of P in acidic soil may be related with better availability of P as the rates of P application increased. Furthermore, plant did have better performance due to liming, which may come from the effect of lime in neutralizing soil acidity and in turn improve the availability of P for crops. Similar result was also reported by (Singh and Tripathib, 1994).

Table 2. Mean value of lime on growth performance of haricot bean varieties at Gununo and Dolla in 2011/12- 2014

Gununo				
Lime (tha ⁻¹)	Varieties	Height	Branch. No	Leaf No
0	Omo-95	42.61	2.55	10.42
	Hawassa dume	38.39	3.46	12.98
0.4	Omo-95	43.25	2.70	9.72
	Hawassa dume	46.83	2.85	9.90
CV		39.59	17.4	31.7
LSD		4.37g	0.58	1.53

3.3. Effect of lime on yield and yield component of haricot bean varieties

3.3.1 Pods number and length

Analysis of variance showed that there was significant interaction effect of lime and phosphorus rates on number and length of pods for both varieties in two locations. Maximum number and length of pods were recorded at 0.4tha⁻¹ with the absence and also application of lime for Hawassa dume while Omo-95 had lower performance (Table 3). Such increment of pods number and length with increasing rate lime with P may be attributed to the better availability of P for plants as the rate of external P application increase which in turn observed on better plant performance. Furthermore, better performance of both varieties with liming may be related with neutralizing of acid soil by lime which in turn increases availability of P for plant uptake (Kisinyo *et al.*, 2005). Interaction effects of lime and haricot bean varieties were significant whereas P fertilizer had interaction with lime and haricot bean varieties significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected pod number of the hawassa dume variety (Table 3). Highest number of pods per plant (9.35) was produced when the crop was grown with lime. Effect of lime on pod per plant and Pod number recorded from lime treated alone hawassa dume variety alone was not significantly different. This may be because lime created better soil environment for naturally existing haricot bean varieties. This finding is also in line with reports of Malik *et al.* (2006) who indicated more pod number per plant of soybean

3.3.2. Seeds number and seed yields

There was significant variation on seed number per pod and seed yield ha⁻¹ due to application of lime and the two varieties. Maximum number of seeds per pod and seed yield ha⁻¹ at the two locations were recorded for both varieties while they were treated by 0 and 0.4 tha⁻¹ of lime (Table 3). Seeds number and seed yield were increased with increasing rates of lime for the two varieties which were treated by lime at rates of 0 and 0.4tha⁻¹. As stated earlier available P with lime was increased when rates of lime application increased with crop production, these in turn improve crop performance such as seeds and pod number and at the end seed yield. The result may be attributed to the fact that applying phosphorus fertilizer increases crop growth and yield on soils which are naturally low in P and in soils that have been depleted (Mullins, 2001).

The interaction effect of lime and haricot bean varieties were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in terms of seed number per pod of the haricot bean (Table 3). Regardless of P fertilization, lime and hawassa dume gave significantly higher seeds per pod. However, P with and without lime gave significantly more seed yield under the use of hawassa dume variety (Table 3). This result is supported by (Munns *et al.*, 1981; Chalk *et al.*, 2010) who reported beneficial effect of lime for legumes grown in acidic soil. When lime was applied, acidic soils significantly increased seed yield of the haricot bean. This may be because of the fact that acidic soil environment was neutralized by the applied lime. Earlier findings also showed that rhizobium and P fertilizer give almost similar weight in legumes like soybean, haricot bean and mung bean (Munns *et al.*, 1980).

Table 3. Mean value of lime on yield and yield components performance of haricot bean varieties at Gununo in 2012-2014

Gununo					
Lime (tha ⁻¹)	Varieties	Pod No	Seed No	Pod Length	Seed Yield
0	Omo-95	8.8	5.42	8.35	826.32
	Hawassa dume	9.25	5.17	8.47	930.3
0.4	Omo-95	8.77	5.02	8.17	1079.40
	Hawassa dume	9.35	5.17	8.47	1282.49
CV		27.7	17.14	9.5	34.27
LSD		1.43	0.44	0.57	201

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A field experiments was conducted at the two locations on acidic soil to study the effect of lime on haricot bean varieties at Gununo in Wolaita Zone, Southern Ethiopia. The research work was initiated to evaluate the response of haricot bean varieties to liming on acid soils. The experiment was laid out in factorial randomized complete block design with three replications. Hawassa dume and Omo-95 were treated by 0 and 0.4 tha⁻¹ of lime.

Soil samples were collected from the location before sowing and at maturity for analysis of some selected physical and chemical properties of soil (texture, Soil pH, Av.P, OC, and TN). Laboratory analysis resulted of the soil samples taken before sowing and at harvest revealed that all the soil parameters were at lower rates even though the soil was treated by different rates of lime.

Available Phosphorus showed increasing tendency with increasing soil pH and liming on both in seasons. The overall result of chemical properties in this study, demonstrated that most soil parameters were significantly different with lime application at two areas.

There was a significant increase on growth parameters of the two varieties as rates of lime increased at Gunn sites. Maximum values of plant height, leaves and branches number were recorded at application rates at both location with liming in year1&2. Similarly, the highest grain yield and yield components were obtained at 20 kg P ha⁻¹ with lime (0.4 tha⁻¹) on both varieties at location. Furthermore, application of lime improved soil conditions and in turns varieties performance at both years.

Therefore, applying of liming materials in acidic soil maximize the availability of nutrients especially phosphorus in the soil, which is very important for better performance of crops. In general liming is important in the study area; this is because of strong acidity and low values of some chemical properties of the soil. The application of P fertilizer increased yields of haricotbean; however, the grain yields were low compared with crop potential. This indicates that a two season treatment of lime can correct problem of soil acidity. So it is recommended that correcting of soil acidity should be done for growth seasons until soil comes to neutral conditions and increased crop production.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are hugely indebted to wolita Sodo University for the research work grant (Grant number WSU/2004/01) and following us to do our research concern. We are particularly grateful for the Agricultural Office of Wolaita Zone, Damot Sore Rural Development Office for their willingness to give as information, guidance and encouragement and for their valuable time. Our thanks go to the development agents working in the researches sites. Therefore, we would like to extend our deepest gratitude to them for their continuous technical support and commitment during the whole path of the research work. Finally, we are indebted to the Department of Plant Science of Wolaita Sodo University for their contribution in the process of developing the research proposal and provision of various services

6. REFERENCES

- Anetor, Mercy Omogbohu and Ezekiel Akinkunmi Akinrinde (2007), "Lime effectiveness of some fertilizers in a tropical acid alfisol", University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria
- CACC (Central Agricultural Census Commission). (2002). Report on the Preliminary Results of Area, Production and Yield of Temporary Crops (Meher Season, Private Peasant Holdings) Part I. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. 200 p
- Chalk, P.M., B.J.R. Alves, R.M. Boddey and S. Urquiaga (2010). Integrated effects of abiotic stresses on inoculants performance, legume growth and symbiotic dependence estimated by 15 N dilution. *Plant Soil*, 328: 1-16
- Gemechu Gedno (1990). Haricot bean (*Phaseolus Vulgaris L.*) Agronomic Research at Bako. Research on Haricot bean in Ethiopia: an Assessment of Status, Progress, Priorities and Strategies. Proceeding of a National Workshop held in AddisAbaba, 1-3 October 1990. 114p.
- Havlin, J.L., J.D. Beaton, S.L. Tsidale, and L. Nelson, (1999). Fertility and Fertilizers. An Introduction to Nutrient Management (6th ed). Prentice Hall. Inc. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
- Herrera, E., (2005). Soil Test Interpretation. Guide A – 122. College of Agriculture and Home Economics. New Mexico State University phosphorus deficiency. *Oxford Journal of Sciences*, 94(3):323-332.
- Kisinyo, C.o. Othieno, j.r. Okalebo, m.j. Kipsat, a.k. Serem & D.o. Obiero (2005). Effects of lime and phosphorus application on early growth of *Leucaena* in acid soils moi University, School of Agriculture and Biotechnology, Eldoret, Kenya
- Malik, M. A., M. A. Cheema, H. Z. Khan and M. W. Ashfaq (2006). Growth and yield response of soybean (*Glycine max L.*) to seed inoculation and varying phosphorus levels. *Journal of Agricultural Research* 44(1):47-53
- Mullins G., (2001). Phosphorus, agriculture & the environment. Virginia Cooperative Extension, Virginia state university. No: 424-029.
- Onwueme, I.C. and T.D. Sinha, (1999). Field Crop Production in Tropical Africa. CTA. Wageningen, Netherlands.
- Oster, J.D., (1982). Gypsum usage in irrigated Agriculture. A review. *Fert. Res.* 3:73-89.
- Ponette, Q., Belkacem, S. & Nys, C., (1996). Ion dynamics in acid forest soil as affected by addition of Ca fertilizers. *Geoderma* 71(1996) 53-76.
- Sahlemedhin Sertsu, Taye Bekele, Yesuf Assen, Amanuel Gofu, Mohammed Hassena, D.G. Tanner, Tesfaye Tesemma, and Takele Gebre. (2000). Optimizing fertilizer use in Ethiopia: Correlation of soil analysis with fertilizer response in Hetosa Wereda, Arsi Zone. Addis Ababa: Sasakawa-Global 2000
- Smith, C.J., Peoples, M.B., Keerthisinghe, G., James, T.R., Garden, D.L. & Tuomi, S.S., (1994). Effects of surface applications of lime, gypsum and phosphogypsum on the alleviating of surface and subsurface acidity in a soil under pasture. *Aust. J. Soil Res.* 32:995-1008.
- Singh, D.N., and Tripathi, P., (1994), Effect of NPK fertilizers and spacing on growth and yield of French bean. *Veg. Sci.*, 21:7-11.
- Tisdal, S. L., W.L. Nelson, J.D. Beaton and D.L. Havlin, (1995). Soil Fertility and Fertilizer (5th ed.). Macmillan Publishing Company. Pp634

Cite this Article: Kassa M, Yebo B and Habte A, 2014. Liming Effects on Yield and Yield Components of Haricot Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) Varieties Grown in Acidic Soil at Damot Sore District, Southern Ethiopia. *Greener Journal of Plant Breeding and Crop Science*, 2 (4): 076-081.